

JAVASCRIPTDA OB'EKTLARNI YARATISH VA ULARGA MUROJAT QILISH

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Anotatsiya: Bu tezis JavaScriptda ob'ektlar yaratish va ularga murojat qilishning asosiy qismini taqdim etadi. Bu mavzu dasturchilar uchun juda muhimdir, chunki ob'ektlar ma'lumotlarni saqlash, ularga qo'shimcha funksiyalar yaratish va ularga murojat qilishga imkon beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: JavaScript, ob'ekt, yaratish, murojat, xususiyat, funksiya, prototip, **proto**.

JavaScriptda ob'ektlar yaratish va ularga murojat qilish, bu tilning asosiy xususiyatlari dan biridir. Ob'ektlar, ma'lumotlarni saqlash va boshqarish uchun ishlatiladigan konteynerlardir. Har bir ob'ekt, o'zining xususiyatlari va metodlari bilan belgilanadi.

Ob'ektlarni yaratish uchun oddiy sintaksisdan foydalanish mumkin:

```
let myObj = {}; // bo'sh ob'ekt yaratish
```

Yoki xususiyatlari bilan birlikda yaratish:

```
let myObj = {  
  name: "John",  
  age: 30,  
  city: "New York"  
};
```

Ob'ekt xususiyatlariga murojat qilish uchun, bu xususiyatlar nomi yordamida amalga oshiriladi:

```
let myObj = {  
  name: "John",  
  age: 30,  
  city: "New York"  
};
```

```
console.log(myObj.name); // "John" ni konsolga chiqarish
```

Ob'ektlar JavaScriptda o'zgartirib bo'lmaydigan elementlar hisoblanadi, ya'ni ular yaratilganidan keyin o'zgartirib bo'lmaydi. Misol uchun:

```
const myObj = {  
  name: "John",  
  age: 30,  
  city: "New York"  
};
```

```
myObj.age = 31; // age qiymatini 31-ga o'zgartirish
```

Ob'ektlarga yangi xususiyatlar va metodlar ham qo'shishingiz mumkin. Buning uchun, ob'ektni nomi bilan yozib, yangi xususiyat yoki metod nomini ko'rsatishingiz kerak:

```
let myObj = {  
  name: "John",  
  age: 30,
```

```
city: "New York"
};
```

```
myObj.gender = "male"; // yangi gender xususiyatini qo'shish
myObj.sayHello = function() {
  console.log("Salom!");
}; // yangi sayHello metodini qo'shish
```

Ob'ektning tarkibida boshqa ob'ekt ham bo'lishi mumkin. Misol uchun:

```
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  address: {
    street: "123 Main St",
    city: "New York",
    state: "NY"
  }
};
```

```
let myStreet = myObj.address.street; // myObj ob'ektidagi address ob'ektining street
xususiyati qiymatini olish
```

JavaScriptda ob'ekt yaratish va ularga murojat qilish, tilni o'rganuvchilar uchun asosiy konseptlardan biridir. Ob'ektlar ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun juda foydali bo'lib, klasslar yaratishda ham ishlatiladi. JavaScriptda, ob'ektlar referensiya hisoblanadi, ya'ni ob'ektning qiymati, o'zining xususiyatlari va metodlaridan iborat bo'lsa ham, ularni yorituvchi xususiyatlar bo'lmaydi. Misol uchun:

```
let obj1 = {name: "John"};
let obj2 = obj1;
obj2.name = "Bob";
console.log(obj1.name); // Bob
console.log(obj2.name); // Bob
```

JavaScriptda ob'ektlar soniya va matnlar kabi primitiv qiymatlari ham o'z ichiga olgan holda yaratiladi va ularga murojat qilish uchun amallar bajarish mumkin:

```
javascript
let myObj = {
  num: 123,
  str: "Hello",
  bool: true,
  nullValue: null,
  undefinedValue: undefined
};
console.log(myObj.num); // 123
console.log(myObj.str); // "Hello"
console.log(myObj.bool); // true
console.log(myObj.nullValue); // null
console.log(myObj.undefinedValue); // undefined
```

Ob'ektlarda qidirish ham amalga oshirilishi mumkin. Buning uchun, for...in sikli ishlatiladi:

```
javascript
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  city: "New York"
};
for(let prop in myObj) {
  console.log(prop + ": " + myObj[prop]);
}
// Konsolga chiqadi:
// name: John
// age: 30
// city: New York
```

delete operatori yordamida, ob'ektning xususiyatlarini o'chirish ham amalga oshirilishi mumkin:

```
javascript
let myObj = {
  name: "John",
  age: 30,
  city: "New York"
};
delete myObj.city; // city xususiyatini o'chirish
console.log(myObj); // {name: "John", age: 30}
```

JavaScriptda, ob'ektlar referensiya hisoblanadi, ya'ni ob'ektning qiymati, o'zining xususiyatlari va metodlaridan iborat bo'lsa ham, ularni yorituvchi xususiyatlar bo'lmaydi.

Misol uchun:

```
javascript
let obj1 = {name: "John"};
let obj2 = obj1;
obj2.name = "Bob";
console.log(obj1.name); // Bob
console.log(obj2.name); // Bob
```

obj1 va obj2 o'zaro teng qiymatga ega bo'lsalar ham, ularning tarkibi ikkalasi uchun bir xil hisoblanadi. Buning sababi, ob'ektlar yaratilganda, ularning qiymatlari o'zgaruvchilarda emas, balki xotiradagi joylarda saqlanadi. Shuning uchun, ob'ektlarni nusxalash yoki o'zgartirishlarini amalga oshirishdan oldin, ob'ektning nusxasi yaratilishi tavsiya etiladi. JavaScriptda ob'ektlar, boshqa dasturlash tillaridagi sinfgil ob'ektlariga o'xshash, balki boshqa dasturlash tillarida ham yordamchi qo'llanmalar yordamida ishlatiladi. Ob'ektlarni yaratish va ularga murojat qilish, JavaScript dasturlashining asosiy qismi hisoblanadi.

Xulosa

JavaScriptda ob'ektlar dasturlashning asosiy qismini tashkil etadi va shu sababli, ularni yaratish va ularga murojat qilishni tushunish juda muhimdir. Ob'ektlar, dasturchilarga, bir-

biridan farqli xususiyatlarga ega bo'lgan ma'lumotlarni bir joyda saqlash, qo'shimcha funksiyalarni o'z ichiga olgan holda foydalanish, va xil ob'ektga asoslanuvchi boshqa ob'ektlarni yaratish imkonini beradi. Ob'ektlarni yaratish, ularga ma'lumot qo'shish va ulardan foydalanish, dasturchilar uchun ko'p foydali bo'lgan asosiy konseptlar hisoblanadi va JavaScriptni o'rganishning boshlang'ich bosqichlari davomida kelib chiqadigan eng muhim mavzulardan biri.

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